

FEATURES OF THE CLASSIFICATION OF TYPES OF GEOTECHNOLOGICAL TERMINOLOGY IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: The article discusses the features of the classification of types of geotechnological terminology in English. For the development of science and technology, the processes of interethnic and international cooperation are a characteristic feature, which inevitably affects the trends in terminological names.

Key words: feature, English, type classifications, geotechnological terminology

Modern processes of formation of new terms in the term mining system increase the requirements for the functioning of these terms. Their main purpose is to enable communication between specialists in the mining industry. For the development of science and technology, the processes of interethnic and international cooperation are a characteristic feature, which inevitably affects the trends in terminological names. All this leads to the use of international means of term formation, as well as to the direct borrowing of terminological names.

The research material in this section was 50 lexical units with the subject of geotechnological terminology. Let us analyze the main ways of forming the terms of this subject.

The formation of new terms as a result of the disintegration of a word into homonyms, that is, the acquisition of new meanings by the same lexical unit, is called the lexico-semantic method of term formation. Over time, the various

meanings of a polysemantic term may lose their semantic connection with each other and turn into independent words, that is, homonyms.

This method of formation can be traced on the example of the term: *control wells* - *nazorat quduqlari*, wells designed to determine the material composition of the ore body and the degree of extraction of its useful component, to be drilled at a particular location of the ore body.

Another lexico-semantic way of forming terms in English geotechnological terminology is borrowing. Terms can be borrowed from other terminology of the English language, from common vocabulary, as well as from other languages. The quantitative composition of English geotechnological terminology is equal to the amount of knowledge at each historical stage in the development of mining. So, for example, in the Roman period, descriptions of minerals, rocks, technical means and methods of production appear. A large number of borrowings in the terminology of mining were taken from the German language, because it was in English that the first printed works on mining appeared. It is worth noting the fact that the German mining terminology is based on the terms of the Latin and ancient Greek languages.

The borrowing of foreign vocabulary mainly goes through two channels: sound borrowing and tracing. In the first case, the sound composition of the word, its outer shell, is borrowed, in the second case, the word-formation structure of the word, that is, the sign of the concept underlying its name. Consequently, words borrowed from other languages include all lexical units, the appearance of which in one language is associated with copying the external or internal structure of the corresponding prototypes in other languages.

Borrowings from the terminology of the English language can be seen in the following examples: *working solution* – *ishchi eritma*, *mining surveyor* - *mina o'lchovchisi*, *worn auger* - *shnek*, *zink* - *sink*, *soil* - *tuproq*.

The most frequent are borrowings from common vocabulary. So, for example, the words: *room* – *xona*, in English, geotechnological terminology will matter -

stope; *pillar* - *ustun*, *novda* - *kamera chuqurligi*; in geotechnology - reservoir, soil; in English geotechnology terminology - application (of fertilizers); word *pit-chuqur*, moved from common vocabulary to mining terminology with the meaning- *ishlab chiqarish*.

Borrowing from other term systems is also quite common. This can be seen in the example of the following terms: haul truck - in automotive terminology, this term means a truck, and in mining - a mine dump truck; cobalt - the term was borrowed from the term of the chemistry system with the transfer of meaning from a chemical element to a solid silver-white metal with a reddish tint; the term elephant trunk was borrowed from construction terminology, in which it means - a concrete ladle swivel funnel, into mining terminology with the meaning - hydraulic elevator; the term ground control was borrowed from the aviation term of the system, in which it matters - the control of ground movement, in the terminology of mining as - the control of a rock mass; the verb to manage - to manage, was borrowed from management terminology, into the term mining system with the meaning - to develop deposits; the term air way, meaning in aviation terminology - an airline, an air route, was borrowed into the term mining system with a meaning - a ventilation drift.

The synonymy of mining terminology is also quite common. Due to the incomplete ordering of the English language of geotechnological terminology, the same term expresses several concepts, which is called polysemy, or different terms are used to express the same concept, which is synonymy. Many synonymous terms are incorrectly orienting and may contradict the essence of the concepts they express and create false ideas.

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